

SROC III

Third **S**erbian **R**adiation **O**ncology **C**ongress

Abstract book

**November, 2-3rd 2024,
Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula, Vrdnik**

MicroRNAs as biomarkers of radiation toxicity in glioblastoma

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13982381

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Radiation therapy is a cornerstone in the treatment of glioblastoma, yet it often results in significant acute toxicity. Recent studies have identified microRNAs (miRNAs) as promising biomarkers for predicting radiation-induced toxicity in glioblastoma patients. MiRNAs are small, non-coding RNA molecules that regulate gene expression and play critical roles in cellular responses to radiation. Notably, miR-21, miR-34a, miR-146a, miR-10b, and miR-210 have been implicated in modulating radiation sensitivity and toxicity. Elevated levels of miR-21 have been associated with increased resistance to radiation and poor prognosis. MiR-34a is known to enhance radiation-induced apoptosis, suggesting its potential as a marker for radiosensitivity. MiR-10b has shown potential as a biomarker for grading the severity of acute radiotoxicity in patients with glioblastoma. Additionally, miR-146a has been linked to inflammatory responses and may serve as an indicator of acute radiation toxicity. MiR-210 is involved in hypoxia pathways, which are critical in the tumor microenvironment and radiation response. Profiling these miRNAs in glioblastoma patients undergoing radiotherapy could enable clinicians to predict and manage adverse effects more effectively, tailoring treatments to individual patient profiles. Furthermore, integrating miRNA profiling with other molecular and clinical parameters could enhance the precision of toxicity predictions. Future research should focus on validating these miRNA biomarkers in larger, multi-center studies and exploring their integration into clinical practice. This personalized approach holds promise for improving the therapeutic

index of radiation therapy, minimizing toxicity, and enhancing the quality of life for patients with glioblastoma.

Keywords: microRNA, glioblastoma, radiation toxicity, biomarker

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2024**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

CIP – Каталогизacija у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (3 ; 2024 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Third Serbian Radiation Oncology
Congress, SROC III, November, 2nd-3rd 2024, Ethno Complex
Vrdnicka Kula, Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. – Novi
Sad : Institut za onkologiju Vojvodine, 2024 (Novi Sad : NS
digiprint). – 60 str. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200. – Str. 3: Introduction / Olivera Ivanov.

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 155485193